

**“INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC-ONLINE CONFERENCE FORMATION
OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE”**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6349890>

Sheraliyeva Shoira

*Jizzakh branch of the National University
of Uzbekistan Faculty of Psychology
Philology and foreign languages first year
Student*

Abstract: *The science of pedagogy alone cannot achieve perfection. It, like other sciences, makes use of the achievements of the social sciences and enriches its content. The knowledge created by mankind today and theories that provide information about the future will be to some extent a source for the science of pedagogy. Like other disciplines, pedagogy serves the social maturity of everyone. It is based on information about the rules of development of nature and society and is itself evolving as a social science.*

Keywords: Patriotic, Pedogogy, Psychology, Occupational Psychology, Philology, Sharia.

INTRODUCTION

First of all, every student, teacher-coach must know the history of his homeland, love it, be patriotic. It is impossible to engage in pedagogical activity without knowledge of the history of education, the history of pedagogy. In order to better understand the theory of pedagogy, it is necessary to know its past development. In order to understand the essence of education on a scientific basis, it is necessary to know the laws of its development in a clear historical Sharia. Therefore, pedagogy as one of the social sciences develops in close connection with the social sciences. The goals and objectives of education are history, philosophy, economics, sociology, ethics, aesthetics, general psychology, youth psychology, pedagogical psychology, occupational psychology, family psychology, social psychology, human psychology, military psychology and psychology, communities with children's hygiene, pediatrics, medicine, cybernetics and other sciences. We analyze the relationship with the science of psychology. In educating students, educators need to know mental processes such as intuition, perception, imagination, attention, thinking and memory. Therefore, the science of pedagogy works separately with the science of psychology. Each science is constantly evolving, relying on its own internal scientific directions in enriching its theories in its development. At the present time, the knowledge created by mankind and information about the future, the various disciplines that provide information, to a certain extent, become a source for the science of pedagogy. Like other disciplines, pedagogy serves the general perfection of every human being.

Teachers and educators play a key role in educating, informing and educating young people, based on psychology and social factors. That is, determine the effect of an effect, the learner determines a plan of action based on intuition, perception, imagination, attention, and

knowledge of how the thought-process is going. Thus, the science of pedagogy is inextricably linked with disciplines such as psychology and sociology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The science of philology serves as a methodological basis for the science of pedagogy. Because the achievements of modern educational theory are the product of the struggle and development of philosophical ideas. Philosophy equips pedagogy with scientific methods, is a source for the development of objective principles of education and upbringing.

The theory of education (didactics) and the theory of education are important components of the science, as the science of pedagogy focuses on two important aspects of personal development - teaching and educating him. Theory of education (didactics) - problems such as intellectual development of the individual, the essence, stages, principles, laws of the educational process, the unity of the teacher and the teacher, the content, form, methods and tools of teaching, ways to improve the educational process examines. Education is divided into general and special types. General education is aimed at providing the information necessary for the development of each person and his ability to organize life activities. The knowledge acquired on the basis of general education will be the basis for further special education, which will enable the individual to receive professional training in the future.

Education is a process of pedagogical activity aimed at training a well-rounded person and a qualified specialist. and reflects the formed worldview. Tasks of pedagogical science. The science of pedagogy makes a special contribution to the development of society based on the fulfillment of the social order in the formation of the individual. The content of social relations, the structure of the state and society, the essence of the ideas that play a leading role in its life play an important role in defining the goals and objectives of pedagogical science.

In the context of building a democratic, humane and legal society in the Republic of Uzbekistan, this science solves the priority task of developing a system of educating well-rounded individuals and qualified specialists, creative development of the theory of education and upbringing based on the idea of national independence. In this process, attention is paid to the following tasks:

1. To study the essence of the pedagogical process aimed at educating a well-rounded person and a qualified specialist.
2. Defining the laws of personal development.
3. Improving the system of continuing education based on the experience of developed countries in the field of education, based on the level of social development.
4. Substantiate the content of the activities of educational institutions and teachers working in them.
5. Generalization and implementation of best pedagogical practices.
6. Equipping teachers with knowledge of pedagogical theory and methods of education.

7. To study the pedagogical conditions for ensuring the interaction between the educational unit and the direction of social education.

8. Creation of effective technologies of teaching and educational process.

9. Development of scientific and methodological recommendations for parents on the successful organization of family education.

Mankind's struggle for survival and protection from various natural disasters have served as the basis for the formation of educational ideas. Due to the fact that people lived in groups in the primitive community system, the members of the group shared the experience of organizing activities for the survival of children (fruits, roots, hunting). Knowledge is often acquired through work and play. Due to the sexual nature of the organization of labor, the upbringing of boys and girls has its own peculiarities. The emergence of the family, private property and the state led to radical changes in the content of social education, the emergence of slaves. It was from this period that education began to be organized on the basis of social demands and needs of society.

CONCLUSION

Thoughts on the purpose, tasks, content and means of educating free citizens have played an important role in the works of Democrats, Plato and Aristotle. In the works of thinkers, these ideas are expressed not as an independent pedagogical theory, but as an important component of philosophical harassment or the project of organizing society. During this period, the initial foundations for the formation of the system of natural and social sciences were laid, and the system of education served only slaves and their children, as the rights of those who were not free in slavery were limited.

REFERENCES:

[1] Bolotova A.K. Прикладная психология: Учебник для вузов / А.К. Bolotova - М. Gardariki, 2006, -382

[2] Yenikeyev M.I. Общая и Социальная психология: Учебник для вузов - М. Norma. 2005, -624

[3] Zarochenskiy K.D. Xudyakova A.T. Experimental psychology: Textbook, ТК VelbiIzd-vo Prospekt, 2005-208 С

[4] Karimova V.M. Psychology. Study guide. T.A

Qodiriy National Heritage Publishing House, "UALBNT" Center, 2002-205